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Authentic leadership to improve individual performance through value congruence and individual creativity of Indonesian sharia commercial bank employees

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Abstract

This study aims to analyze the influence between variables, namely authentic leadership, value congruence, individual creativity and individual performance. Respondents in this study were 98 employees at PT BSI Sub Branch Office in Surabaya, Indonesia. This study uses a quantitative approach with data analysis using PLS (Partial Least Square). The results showed that authentic leadership had a significant positive effect on the value congruence, authentic leadership had a significant positive effect on individual creativity, authentic leadership had a significant positive effect on the individual performance, value congruence had a significant positive effect on individual creativity, value congruence has a significant positive effect on the individual performance, individual creativity has a significant positive effect on the individual performance. Based on this research, the company can improve employee's individual performance through authentic leadership that has value congruence and individual creativity.

Keywords: Authentic leadership; Individual creativity; Individual performance; Value congruence

1. Introduction

In the banking business process, one of the factors that influence the quality of a service is the culture of the organization/company. The service will be of good quality or satisfactory if the service can provide good service to the user community. If people feel disappointed or dissatisfied with the services provided, it indicates that the service is inefficient or of poor quality. Assessments from customers can give a positive or negative image and the results of the assessment depend on the service provided by the employee. Employee performance can determine the quality and image of the company itself.

Employee performance also affects the change of leadership. Changes in leadership or certain positions are part of the mutations and rotations that often occur in the company. The role of leadership to encourage creative behavior of employees is very important considering the leadership authority in shaping various aspects of the organization and work environment and authentic leaders influence work design in such a way as to provide employees with opportunities to work in complex jobs [1]. For companies that have the intention to uphold their commitment to stakeholders, focus is on developing authentic leaders [2]. thus, the need for value congruence which can be the key to success for the company.

There are various types of leadership styles that are widely discussed by experts including transformational, transactional, situational, service and authentic leadership styles with different approaches. Transformational leadership calls for greater consideration of employees' moral values in their efforts to increase their ethical awareness.

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Situational approach emphasizes more on the dimensions of direction and support dimensions, Service Leadership is more likely to prioritize the needs, interests and aspirations of the people they lead above herself. This is different from the authentic leadership style which emphasizes the process of leadership that results from a combination of individual psychological skills with a well-established organizational context to produce behavior with a high level of alertness and capacity for self-control, as well as encourage positive self-development. The transformational, transactional, situational, service and authentic leadership styles have an important role in achieving organizational goals which are realized by increasing performance and commitment from their subordinates. Authentic leadership style is one type of leadership by applying consistent behavior or attitudes to the leader's attitudes, thoughts and actions.

Then, employee performance can also be influenced by the suitability of values, as the appropriate values of each individual person as well as the values adopted by the organization. Values underlie that individuals want if their values are in line with the values in the organization, individuals will feel the organization as a place where individuals can work and then achieve their goals [3]. According to [4] very little research has been done to investigate differences in the relationship between value congruence and the results of hiring employees with different attributes. Organizations seeking value-matched, employees need to use more focused selection or socializing methods to ensure value congruence and individual employees participating in an organization have varying degrees of value congruence and can make it difficult to identify congruence of values for particular levels of employees.

An employee also needs to be able to think creatively, in order to be able to solve the problems he faces [5]. Creativity can develop if it is supported by both internal and external environmental factors. With high creativity, human resources tend to be interested and challenged to solve various problems. A recent study on leadership, creativity and innovation found that they did not find enough primary studies to examine the relationship between creativity and authentic leadership. [6].

In this regard, Human Resources is one of the important factors that can improve and maximize employee performance. Employee performance can be determined by knowing the existing human resources in the bank already have a commitment or not to achieve the organization's goals, namely profit. Commitment to an organization reflects the degree to which an individual identifies with the organization and is committed to its goals. Organizational commitment is also a distinct desire to maintain organizational affiliation, identification with goals, organizational success, employee loyalty, and willingness to make significant efforts for the organization [7].

The results of previous research conducted by [8] explaining the relationship between authentic leadership and personal performance; examining the continuous mediation of employee emotional engagement and personal creativity has research limitations regarding the mediating relationship of value suitability that have not been discussed further and become the basis for this study.

1.1. Literature Review & Development Hypothesis

1.1.1. Authentic Leadership

According to [9], authentic leadership is a leader who has an attitude of upholding values and is more prepared to face challenges in the organization. Those who lead others and present their true selves rather than their unrealistic and false selves are called authentic leaders [10]. Authentic leadership aims to rebuild shareholder trust in the organization [11]. In the world of organizations, authentic leadership is a new type of leadership. This leadership combines traits, behaviors, styles, and skills, which have a positive value for a leader for his organization.

The types of authentic leadership consist of four different basic elements, but all four are related [12]. The four elements are:

- Self-discipline and sincerity. True leaders know their own strengths and weaknesses. True leaders also don't behave differently under different conditions, meaning they are alone in front of their followers. Leaders who use this leadership style do not hesitate to show their failure when they find it.
- Mission oriented and results oriented. True leaders can place the mission of achieving the goals of the crowd or organization above personal goals. His work goals focus on collective achievement, not on personal material accomplishments.
- Authentic leaders are not afraid to show their emotions, but that doesn't mean they are gentle, but can communicate their feelings in the right way.
- Authentic leaders refer to long-term results. They dedicate themselves to providing guidance and direction to the organization with tenacity and patience.

Along with ethical or transformative leadership, genuine leadership belongs to a group of positive forms of leadership [13]. [14] believes that this type of leadership is veritably important in moment s competitive terrain to ameliorate the relationship between directors and inferiors, as opposed to a further hierarchical style of leadership. Moreover, authentic leadership emerged in reaction to the request for leaders who act with duty, judgment, straightforwardness and profound quality [15].

1.1.2. Value Congruence

Particular values are defined as broad, situational, and desirable pretensions that are seen as guiding principles in one's life. These value traits have consequences for individual choices and behavior. First, values represent goals that people find desirable; They reflect preferences for what is considered valuable and important. Values therefore serve as a strong impetus to action. Second, particular values are the cognitive representations of the beginning motivational pretensions. Third, individual values are classified according to their private significance. The more important the value, the more motivated the person is to calculate on this value as a guiding principle. [16].

Value congruence refers to the comity or parallels in particular values between a leader and his followers. When leaders and workers work toward the same vision, they tend to develop more analogous core values. similar gests increase interpersonal trust, particular connection and eventually the provocation of followers. Value congruence is an important and common part of trusting connections. Trust is an important factor in gaining hand support for change [17].

Value congruence between employees and their organizations complements the delegation of decision-making, surrogate monitoring is also associated with behavioral support for organizational change. There are four key explanations of the effect of intra-organizational value alignment, surrounded in terms of communication, consistency, interpersonal fascination, and believe. Organizational values are defined as criteria for employee evaluation of desirable or undesirable events, conditioning and individualities. Organizational values shape the private and internal aspects of culture. It indicates an acceptable and realistic solution to an organization's problems. An organization's values reflect the overall goals and standards of an organization. Organizations align individual employee values with organizational values and allow individuals to complement the organization [18].

1.1.3. Individual Creativity

According to [19], creativity is an ability possessed by a person in producing/creating/conducting something new in solving the problem at hand, furthermore something new can be in the form of objects, ideas, ideas, models, strategies and so on. that are useful/valuable for themselves and others. Individual creativity embodies creative thinking abilities, including flexibility, fluency, and uniqueness in social and organizational psychology. Individual creativity is often considered the most important element of organizational innovation, this kind of creativity relies upon on the social context and relationships in which an person is embedded [20].

According to [21], the prerequisites that must be met in building creativity are:

- Have extensive knowledge and be able to solve any problems encountered.
- Have self-quality which includes self-confidence, cheerful, independent, hardworking, and always ready to face the risks.
- Have a high ability to concentrate, where there is a balance in himself, and have an internal drive to always think brilliantly.

1.1.4. Individual Performance

According to [22], performance is the result of an employee's work over a period of time based on the job description. The benefits of individual performance for the organization and its employees are [23]:

- Improving performance, namely that they are aware of their duties at work, so they want to continue to improve their performance.
- Compensation adjustments, namely that compensation has an important position for workers in creating their creativity.
- Investment decisions, namely activities that include self-promotion, which are carried out in doing work to the maximum/
- Training needs and development needs assessment. Train and develop employees to optimize their performance.

- Plan and develop aircraft carriers. driving to identify the types of careers and potential careers that are possible.
- Help explain and identify errors that occur, which can hinder the effectiveness of work within the organization.
- The selected job opportunities have been based on careful thought and not from discriminatory decisions.

Performance is the result achieved by an individual or group in the organization by completing their responsibilities according to the standards set. Performance can also be referred to as the level of individual success when carrying out tasks and responsibilities holistically for a certain period. In addition, the completion of tasks, either by a person or a group of people in their work, can also be called performance [24]. Performance consists of several parts, including:

- Quality of work, is part of the work. This result is said to be qualified if it meets a number of prerequisites or ideal standards from the company/organization.
- Quantity of work, related to the amount produced through a job in accordance with the achievement target.
- Work knowledge refers to a number of information or cognitive abilities possessed by individuals in certain fields.
- Work independence, is about how a staff can do the work that is their responsibility without involving leadership assistance or requiring leadership intervention.

1.1.5. Conceptual Framework

The conceptual framework compiled by the author consists of independent and dependent variables and Intervening variables. The independent variable consists of Authentic leadership (X) and the dependent variable is Individual performance (Y), while the intervening variable is Value Congruence (Z1) and Individual Creativity (Z2). The conceptual framework of this research is as follows:

Source: designed by Authors

Figure 1 Conceptual Framework

1.1.6. Hypothesis of Research

H1. The effect of authentic leadership on the value congruence.

In the research of [1], congruence in organizational-leadership culture indicates that followers or individuals will be motivated regarding the conformity of organizational and leadership values. In the research of [25] shows that value congruence has a positive effect as a mediation in influencing authentic leadership.

H1: Authentic leadership has a significant effect on the value congruence.

H2. The effect of value congruence on individual creativity of employees.

According to [26], value congruence can increase employee creativity, because it allows workers to more prognosticate their associates' responses to their creative endeavors so that value congruence is positively related to individual creativity. Based on the presented explanation, a hypothesis can be formulated.

H2: Value congruence has a significant effect on individual creativity of employees.

H3. The effect of individual creativity on the individual performance of employees.

Based on the research of [27] from showing that creativity partially and at the same time has a positive and significant effect on employee performance. Research [28] shows that job performance is significantly influenced by employee creativity.

H3: Individual creativity has a significant effect on individual performance of employees.

H4. The effect of authentic leadership on individual creativity of employees.

In a study conducted by [8], a statistically sizeable nice relationship among genuine leadership and worker performance. In [29] research, Authentic leadership does not affect creativity directly, but can influence through work resources through value conformity and affective commitment because it has a positive influence on employee creativity. In the research of [30], it shows that the variables of leadership, workload, creativity have a significant effect on organizational commitment, at the same time as organizational dedication drastically influences worker performance. Based in this description, on this have a look at the hypothesis is formulated as follows:

H4: Authentic leadership has a significant effect on the individual creativity of employees.

H5. The effect of authentic leadership on individual performance of employees.

According to [31], hypothesis results confirm the positive effect of authentic leaders on employee performance as positive leaders' direct employees and organizations to support and use their strengths and consequently deliver good performance. The results of the study [32] also show that authentic leadership has a significant positive effect on individual performance. Based on the explanation above, it can be concluded that the hypothesis:

H5: Authentic leadership has a significant effect on individual performance of employees.

H6. The effect of value congruence on individual performance of employees.

According to [33], alignment with values makes it more likely that employees will agree on other areas such as goals and procedures, which reduces conflict and leads to good performance. Based on this description, the hypotheses that can be formulated are:

H6: Value congruence has a significant effect on individual performance of employees.

2. Material and methods

This research was conducted using a quantitative approach, with ratio data processing as the focus of research to be able to find out how much influence between research variables.

The type of research used is a case study. The research method used is descriptive. The purpose of using case study research and descriptive methods is to analyze the data in detail, namely to provide an overview of the data, which then makes a description of the data, which has been successfully collected at the time the research was conducted.

The population of this research is the employees of PT BSI in the Sub-Branch Office Surabaya, Indonesia, totaling 98 employees.

The sample was obtained by using a saturated sampling technique with the same number as the population of Sub-Branch Office employees in Surabaya, Indonesia, namely 98 people.

Definition of operational variables of each variable as following:

2.1. Authentic Leadership

Authentic leadership, which is defined as an attitude or pattern of behavior possessed by leaders, is known for positive behavior and can create a positive climate, has high awareness and is moral. Have the ability to process information well, have a rational attitude of transparency, and be able to develop themselves positively [34].

Authentic Leadership Indicators according to [32]:

- Self-understanding.
- Relationship Transparency.
- Moral Perspective.
- Balanced Processing.

2.2. Value Congruence

Value congruence is something that indicates that individuals are attracted to organizations where the value system matches their own system [4]. Value congruence indicators according to [35]:

- Employees feel that they always give their best and are responsible.
- Employees feel they work together to achieve goals.
- Employees feel professional and look polite.
- Employees feel clinging to the value of truth and being themselves.

2.3. Individual Creativity

According to [36], individual creativity is the ability to think about things in new and unusual ways and produce unique solutions to the problems at hand. The following are indicators of individual creativity according to [37]:

- Have curiosity and original thinking, and be applied in the desire to learn new things and use new work tools in work.
- Tendency to think divergently and find new ideas and then apply them creatively.
- High thinking ability so as to be able to come up with plans to apply new ideas in work.
- Courage to take risks at work in order to create things that support work and have a good impact.

2.4. Individual Performance

According to [38], performance can be seen in terms of the behavior of each employee that leads to productivity by looking at the quality of work, dependence in work, the contribution given based on his work behavior in carrying out work activities. Employee performance indicators according to [39]:

- Quality
- Quantity/Intensity
- Accuracy
- Effectiveness
- Independence

3. Results

3.1. Model Conceptualization

In this study, the exogenous variables, namely the X variable (Authentic Leadership), and Z1 (Value Congruence) and the Z2 (Individual Creativity) variable, are positioned to give an influence to the endogenous variable, namely the Y variable (Individual Performance) then variable Z gives effect to variable Y.

Source: designed by Authors with SmartPLS

Figure 2 Structural Equation Model

3.2. Outer Model Evaluation

3.2.1. Validity Test

Convergent Validity

Convergent validity is a check of the validity of the measuring version with reflexive indicators. The SmartPLS output for the element procedure offers the subsequent results:

Table 1 Results for Outer Loading

Indicators	Authentic Leadership	Value Congruence	Individual Creativity	Individual Performance
X1	0904			
X2	0901			
X3	0861			
X4	0940			
Z11		0895		
Z12		0825		
Z13		0832		
Z14		0813		
Z21			0916	
Z22			0931	
Z23			0902	
Y1				0880
Y2				0895
Y3				0942
Y4				0859
Y5				0896

Source: processed field data with SmartPLS

The table above indicates that each one variable has a load issue better than the encouraged value of 0.5. The minimal value is 0.813 for the Z1 indicator, whilst the most value is 0.942 for the Y3 indicator. This proves that each one signs used on this examine are legitimate or have a pleasant convergence value.

The following is a diagram of the loading issue of every indicator within side the studies model:

Source: processed field data with SmartPLS

Figure 3 Load factor value

Discriminant Validity

The index of differential validity can be observed during cross-loading between the index and its structure. If the correlation between the structure and its index is greater than the correlation between the index and other structures, this indicates that the latent structure is better at predicting its block index than other block indices.

Table 2 Results for Cross Loading

Indicators	Authentic Leadership	Value Congruence	Individual Creativity	Individual Performance
X1	0.904	0.340	0.479	0.528
X2	0.901	0.241	0.364	0.425
X3	0.861	0.347	0.370	0.398
X4	0.940	0.398	0.451	0.531
Z11	0.425	0.895	0.448	0.509
Z12	0.296	0.825	0.324	0.367
Z13	0.265	0.832	0.341	0.391
Z14	0.229	0.813	0.359	0.367
Z21	0.486	0.411	0.916	0.499
Z22	0.443	0.374	0.931	0.464
Z23	0.350	0.432	0.902	0.519

Y1	0.515	0.380	0.477	0.880
Y2	0.536	0.400	0.461	0.895
Y3	0.462	0.501	0.486	0.942
Y4	0.447	0.534	0.483	0.859
Y5	0.398	0.383	0.506	0.896

Source: processed field data with SmartPLS

An indicator is validated if it shows the highest load factor for the target structure compared to other structural load factors. The above is shown in the table that the load factor for the Authentic Leadership structure (X1 to X4) has a load factor for the related structure which has a higher value than other structures. The same applies to the indexes that make up the following structure, where each index reflects the highest value of the variable in question. Therefore, the latent structure predicts that the index of each block has a better value than the index of the other blocks.

Another manner to have a take a observe discriminant validity is to have a take a observe the value of the rectangular root of the suggest AVE value. The endorsed value is extra than 0.5. Here is the AVE value on this study:

Table 3 Average Variance Extracted (AVE)

Variables	AVE	Squared AVE
Authentic Leadership	0.814	0.902
Value Congruence	0.709	0.842
Individual Creativity	0.840	0.916
Individual Performance	0.801	0.895

Source: processed field data with SmartPLS

The table above suggests that each one constructs have an AVE value more than 0.5, in addition to the rectangular root value of the AVE ensuing in a value more than 0.5, so it meets exact validity check requirements for every variable studied.

Reliability Test

The reliability check is performed by checking the overall reliability value of the structural measurement indicator blocks. The combined confidence results show a satisfactory value when it is greater than 0.7. This is the aggregated confidence value in the output:

Table 4 Composite Reliability

Variables	Composite Reliability
Authentic Leadership	0.946
Value Congruence	0.907
Individual Creativity	0.940
Individual Performance	0.953

Source: processed field data with SmartPLS

The table above suggests that the composite reliability rating for all configurations is more than 0.7, indicating that everyone configurations for the estimation version meet the standards for discriminative validity. The lowest composite reliability rating is 0.907 within side the conformance rating structure. Reliability trying out also can be more suitable with Cronbach's Alpha. In this case, the SmartPLS output suggests the subsequent results:

Table 5 Cronbach's alpha

Variables	Cronbach's Alpha
Authentic Leadership	0.924
Value Congruence	0.864
Individual Creativity	0.904
Individual Performance	0.937

Source: processed field data with SmartPLS

Recommended values are more than 0.6, and the table above indicates the Cronbach's alpha values for all configurations more than 0.6. The minimal value while developing a compliance value is 0.864.

3.3. Structural Model Testing (Inner Model)

After the anticipated model meets the standards for the outer model, the subsequent step is to check the structural model (the internal model). The R-squared value of the assemble is:

Table 6 R Square

Variables	R Square
Value Congruence	0.139
Individual Creativity	0.302
Individual Performance	0.439

Source: processed field data with SmartPLS

The table above gives an R^2 value of 0.139 for the value congruence construct, which means that authentic leadership is able to contribute 13.9% to changes in the value congruence construct. The construct of individual creativity has an R^2 of 0.302 which means that the constructs of authentic leadership and value congruence contribute 30.2% to changes in the construct of individual creativity. Then, the value of 0.439 on the individual performance construct which means that authentic leadership, value congruence, and individual creativity are able to explain the variance of individual performance of 43.9%.

3.4. Hypothesis Testing

The hypothesis on this observe became calculated the usage of the SmartPLS program and the results are according to the table below:

Table 7 Results of Hypothesis Testing

	Original Sample (O)	Sample Mean (M)	Standard Deviation (STDEV)	T Statistics (O/STDEV)	P Values
Authentic Leadership → Value Congruence	0.373	0.380	0.099	3.775	0.000
Authentic Leadership → Individual Creativity	0.350	0.346	0.086	4.072	0.000
Authentic Leadership → Individual Performance	0.299	0.292	0.084	3.578	0.000
Value Congruence → Individual Creativity	0.313	0.323	0.098	3.186	0.002
Value Congruence → Individual Performance	0.255	0.271	0.085	2.989	0.003
Individual Creativity → Individual Performance	0.287	0.283	0.100	2.860	0.004

Source: processed field data with SmartPLS

Then the research findings can be described as follows:

3.4.1. Authentic Leadership towards Value Congruence.

Calculation of data analysis shows that Authentic Leadership has an effect of 0.373 on Value Congruence. This effect is positive and is accompanied by a t-statistic of 3.775 ($t > 1.96$) with a p value of 0.000 ($p < 0.05$) which means that the 1st hypothesis in this study is accepted. In other words, the increase in Authentic Leadership significantly influences the increase in Value Congruence to employees.

3.4.2. Authentic Leadership of Individual Creativity.

Calculation of the results of data analysis shows that Authentic Leadership has an effect of 0.350 on Individual Creativity. The positive effect and accompanied by a t-statistic of 4.072 ($t > 1.96$) with the support of a p value of 0.000 ($p < 0.05$) means that the second hypothesis in this study is accepted. It can also be said that the increase in Authentic Leadership has a significant effect on increasing Individual Creativity in employees.

3.4.3. Authentic Leadership on Individual Performance.

Calculation of data analysis shows that Authentic Leadership has an influence of 0.299 on individual performance. This effect is positive and is accompanied by a t-statistic of 3.578 ($t > 1.96$) with a p value of 0.000 ($p < 0.05$). It can also be said that the third hypothesis in this study is accepted. In other words, the increase in Authentic Leadership significantly influences the increase in individual performance of employees.

3.4.4. Values Congruence to Individual Creativity

Calculations on the data analysis show that the Values Congruence has an effect of 0.313 on Individual Creativity. The positive effect is accompanied by a t-statistic of 3.186 ($t > 1.96$) with the support of a p value of 0.002 ($p < 0.05$), which means that the fourth hypothesis in this study is accepted. It can be said that the increase in Value Congruence significantly affects the increase in Individual Creativity in employees.

3.4.5. Value Congruence to Individual Performance

Calculation of data analysis shows that the Values Congruence has an effect of 0.255 on individual performance. This effect is positive and is accompanied by a t-statistic of 2.989 ($t > 1.96$) with a p value of 0.003 ($p < 0.05$) meaning that the 5th hypothesis in this study is accepted. In other words, the increase in Value Congruence has a significant effect on increasing individual performance of employees.

3.4.6. Individual Creativity on Individual Performance

The results of the calculation of data analysis show that individual creativity has an influence of 0.287 on individual performance. This effect is positive and is accompanied by a t-statistic of 2.860 ($t > 1.96$) with a p value of 0.004 ($p < 0.05$) which gives the answer that the 6th hypothesis in this study is accepted. In other words, an increase in individual creativity has a significant effect on increasing individual performance in employees.

4. Discussion

4.1. Authentic Leadership to Employee Value Congruence.

The results of testing the effect of authentic leadership on the value congruence of PT BSI employees indicate that authentic leadership has a significant positive effect on value congruence. This means that an increase in authentic leadership will significantly increase employee value congruence.

From the analysis results show that authentic leadership indicators provide the greatest contribution to increasing the value congruence on staff. This statement is supported by research that is in line with the research statement [1], congruence in organizational-leadership culture indicates that followers or individuals will be motivated regarding the suitability of organizational and leadership values. In [25] also shows that value congruence has a positive effect as a mediation in influencing authentic leadership.

Based on the explanation above, it can be concluded that there is effect of authentic leadership on the value congruence of employee. Through this research, the increase in authentic leadership has a significant effect on increasing the value congruence of employee.

4.2. Value Congruence to Employee Individual Creativity.

The results of testing the effect of value congruence on individual creativity of PT BSI employees stated that value conformity had a significant positive effect on individual creativity. This can be interpreted that an increase in value congruence will significantly increase the individual creativity of employees.

From the analysis results show that the indicators make a positive contribution to the increase in individual creativity of employees. This is supported by research that is in line with the statement [26], value congruence can increase employee creativity, because it allows employees to better predict the reactions of their co-workers to their creative efforts so as to provide positive values with individual creativity.

Based on the discussion above, it can be concluded that there is an influence between value congruence on individual creativity of employee. In the study, the increase in value congruence significantly gave the effect of increasing the individual creativity of employees.

4.3. Individual Creativity on Employee Individual Performance.

The test results of PT BSI employees on the effect of personal creativity on personal performance indicate that individual creativity has a significant positive effect on employees' personal performance. This means that an increase in individual creativity will significantly improve individual performance. The results of the analysis show that the measurement indicators of individual creativity make a positive contribution to improving the personal performance of employees. This is supported by the existence of similar studies, particularly those conducted by [27] show that creativity has a positive and simultaneous partial and significant effect on employee performance.

From the explanation above, it can be concluded that there is an influence between individual creativity and personal performance of employees. In this study, increasing individual creativity has a significant effect on individual employee performance.

4.4. Authentic Leadership on Employee Individual Creativity.

The experimental results regarding the effect of authentic leadership on individual creativity of PT BSI employees show that authentic leadership has a significant positive effect on individual creativity. This means that the emergence of authentic leadership will greatly increase the personal creativity of employees. The results of the analysis show that the indicators of authentic leadership make a positive contribution to increasing the personal creativity of employees. This is supported by research that is in line with research by [8] that there is a statistically significant positive relationship between authentic religious leadership abilities and personal creativity.

From the explanation above, it can be concluded that there is an influence between authentic leadership on the personal creativity of employees. In this study, the emergence of authentic leadership has a significant effect on the individual creativity of employees.

4.5. Authentic Leadership on Employee Individual Performance.

The results of the research on the effect of Authentic Leadership on individual performance of PT BSI employees indicate that Value Conformity has a significant positive effect on individual performance. This means that an increase in authentic leadership will significantly improve individual employee performance.

Based on the results of the analysis, it was found that the indicators of authentic leadership made a positive contribution to improving employee performance. This is supported by the existence of research that is in line according to [31]. The hypothesis results confirm the positive effect of authentic leaders on employee performance as positive leaders' direct employees and organizations to support and use their strengths and consequently provide successful performance as the results research by [32] also show that authentic leadership has a significant positive effect on individual performance.

Based on the explanation above, it can be concluded that there is an influence between authentic leadership on individual employee performance. In this study, the increase in authentic leadership significantly influences the individual performance of employees.

4.6. Value Congruence to the individual performance of employees.

The results of the research on the effect of value congruence on Individual performance of employee at PT BSI indicate that value congruence has a significant positive effect on individual performance. This means that an increase in value congruence will significantly improve the individual performance of employees.

Based on the research analysis, it can be seen that the value congruence indicator makes a positive contribution to improving individual performance of employee. This is supported by the existence of research that is in line with the research of [33] alignment on values makes it more likely that employees will agree on other areas such as goals and procedures, which reduces conflict resulting in good performance.

Based on the discussion above, an influence can be concluded between the value congruence on individual performance of employee. In this study, the increase in value congruence has a significant effect on increasing the individual performance of employees.

4.7. Managerial Implication

In addition to providing input for organizations/companies, through this, in order to achieve the vision and mission of PT BSI, it must continue to implement values based on morality, namely Competent, Trustworthy, Loyal, Harmonious, Adaptive and Collaborative which are the Core Values of State-Owned Enterprises, in order to compete in conventional banking. PT BSI must continue to develop employee competencies by conducting training and evaluating knowledge in order to compete with conventional banking. Attractive products that are not available in conventional banks can provide solutions for the needs of people in Indonesia. This research also provides input to enrich the theory of the relationship between authentic leadership, individual performance, value congruence and individual creativity.

5. Conclusion

Based on the results of research and discussion, the following conclusions are drawn:

- Authentic leadership has a significant positive effect, which is 0.373 on the value congruence of employees.
- Authentic leadership has a significant positive effect, amounting to 0.350 on the individual creativity of employees.
- Authentic leadership has a significant positive effect, amounting to 0.299 on individual performance of employees.
- Value congruence has a positive and significant effect of 0.313 on the individual creativity of employees.
- Value congruence has a significant positive effect of 0.255 on the individual performance of employees.
- Individual creativity has a significant positive effect of 0.287 on the individual performance of employees.

In an effort to improve the individual performance of PT BSI employees, based on the results of the study, it shows that leaders can use an authentic leadership style that is supported by the value congruence and individual creativity.

Compliance with ethical standards

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Disclosure of conflict of interest

The authors wish to declare that none has any interest to disclose.

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